

Thionyl Bromide as a Polar Solvent

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Monosolvates of thionyl bromide with aluminium bromide, aluminium chloride and boron (III) bromide have been isolated while the existence of the disolvates of aluminium bromide, aluminium chloride and antimony (III) bromide has been indicated conductometrically. Conductance of the solutions has been measured to reveal their nature. It forms 1 : 2-complexes with nitrogen bases. The existence of complexes of other compositions has been indicated conductometrically. Electro-chemical properties like specific, molal and molar conductances of the solutions of complexes have been studied to throw light on their nature. Solid complexes of quaternary ammonium bromides have been isolated and characterised and the degree of dissociation (α) and dissociation constant (K) of these quaternary ammonium bromides have been determined in thionyl bromide.

Its usefulness as a brominating agent consequent upon the release of bromide ions in solution has been studied by carrying out solvolysis of various oxides, carbonates, iodides, formates, acetates, fatty acids, sulphur trioxide and chlorosulphuric acid.

Acid-base neutralisation reactions of various Lewis acids with a number of solvo and ansolvo bases have been carried out conductometrically in thionyl bromide. Wherever possible, the neutralisation complexes have been isolated.

Electrolysis of dilute solutions of bases in thionyl bromide further supports the proposed auto-ionisation of thionyl bromide as :

A few scattered references on the use of thionyl bromide as a brominating agent for certain organic compounds¹⁻⁷ are available in literature. It has a convenient and wide liquid range (-50° to 138°)⁸ but it is unstable above 80° . It has a low dielectric constant (9.06 at 20°)⁹ which may make it a poor solvent for ionic compounds but a good solvent for organic and nonpolar substances. The low value of specific conductance ($< 1 \times 10^{-7}$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 20°) points to the possibility of limited autoionisation of the solvent. Since it is a potential reaction medium for bromides, an attempt is being made to study it as a solvent.

1. H. G. Rule and A. J. G. Barnett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 175.
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4. M. J. Frazer, W. Gerrard, G. Machell and B. D. Shephard, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1954, 931.
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The molecular structure of thionyl bromide may be expected to be a resonance hybrid of the structures I, II and III.

(I)

(II)

(III)

The structure (I) is possible, if the electronegativity of the groups attached to sulphur is high enough to raise its electronegativity to equal that of oxygen¹⁰. This is not expected in thionyl bromide and may be possible if bromine is replaced by fluorine. The sulphur-bromine bond length ($2.27 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$)¹¹ in thionyl bromide is considerably greater than the sum of the covalent radii of sulphur and bromine (2.18 \AA) which points to the possibility of a feeble ionic character of this bond. In the present work, the nature of solutions of Lewis acids, nitrogen bases, ionic bromides; formation of their complexes in the solvent and their characterisation, is being described. Its solvent potentialities have been further explored by a study of the acid-base neutralisation and solvolytic reactions in it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Anhydrous aluminium bromide dissolves in thionyl bromide in an exothermic reaction resulting in the production of conducting solutions. The plot of specific conductance versus concentration as represented by molar ratio Lewis acid/SOBr₂ (Fig. 1) clearly indicates the

FIG. 1—SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE OF ALUMINIUM CHLORIDE, ALUMINIUM BROMIDE AND ANTIMONY (III) BROMIDE IN THIONYL BROMIDE AT 25°C

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11. D. P. Stevenson and R. A. Cooley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2477.

existence of complex $\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{SOBr}_2$ in solution. This study could not be extended to a molar ratio of 1 : 1 due to the separation of a light yellow (1 : 1) complex $\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot \text{SOBr}_2$ which is slightly soluble in solvents like carbon tetrachloride, nitrobenzene and chloroform.

The plot of specific conductance against molar concentration for aluminium chloride in thionyl bromide (Fig. 1) indicates the formation of complexes in solution at molar ratios Lewis acid/ SOBr_2 of 1 : 2 and 1 : 1. The sharp decrease in conductance beyond equimolar ratio may be due to the highly viscous nature of the system. This solution on washing with carbon tetrachloride provides a pale yellow liquid complex $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{SOBr}_2$ which solidifies in an ice-bath. It is extremely hygroscopic and is only slightly soluble in nitrobenzene, methylene chloride and chloroform.

In view of the tetra-coordination of aluminium and the appreciable specific conductance of the complexes in solution, the following ionic species may be postulated :

where X = Cl, Br.

From equilibria (i) and (ii), it is clear that the number of ionic species is the same but the specific conductance of the disolvate is higher than that of the monosolvate (Fig. 1). The higher value of specific conductance for the disolvates may be due to the bigger size of the cation which may lead to a greater degree of ionisation¹². The higher value of specific conductance could also be explained as due to the existence of equilibrium (iii),

but penta coordination of aluminium is not much favoured in view of its stable tetra and hexa coordination. The monosolvates of aluminium bromide and chloride are slightly soluble in nitrobenzene and their molar conductance values at millimolar concentration are 19.69 and 20.10 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$, respectively. This indicates a uni-univalent character of these complexes and supports the mode of ionisation as given in equilibrium (i).

Boron (III) bromide reacts with ice cold thionyl bromide to give an orange yellow complex ($\text{BBr}_3 \cdot \text{SOBr}_2$). It is not very stable and on exposure to atmosphere, it starts decomposing with the evolution of hydrogen bromide and bromine. It is slightly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, methylene chloride and nitrobenzene. The molar conductance of 20.95 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$ in nitrobenzene indicates its uni-univalent character :

Antimony (III) bromide also gives conducting solutions with thionyl bromide and the plot of specific conductance against composition (Fig. 1) indicates the possible existence of the complex $\text{SbBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{SOBr}_2$ in solution. On account of the limited solubility of antimony (III) bromide in thionyl bromide, specific conductance of solutions with a concentration higher than molar ratio of 0.6 could not be determined. In view of the tetracoordination

of antimony, the structure of this complex like that of the other disolvates, may be expressed as :

The above proposed structures are possible only if coordination takes place through a bromine atom of thionyl bromide ($\text{OSBrBr} \cdot \text{MX}_3$) or it acts as a bromide ion donor. However, an examination of the Raman spectra¹³ of the solid complexes of aluminium chloride with thionyl chloride shows a negative shift in $\nu(\text{S} = \text{O})$ stretching frequency on complex formation with aluminium chloride. This has been interpreted on the basis of the formation of a donor acceptor compound with $\text{O} \rightarrow \text{M}$ dative bond :

On analogy it may, therefore, be inferred that coordination through the oxygen atom of the thionyl bromide cannot be neglected in the solid state and this has been confirmed by spectral investigations of various addition complexes of phosphoryl halides¹⁴. However, various competitive equilibria are expected to exist in solution and a bromine bridge formation may occur to some extent thereby leading to the formation of the suggested ionic species. The equilibria existing in solution may be easily shifted by precipitating the most favoured solid phase¹⁵.

FIG 2—SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE OF PYRIDINE, α -PICOLINE AND QUINOLINE IN THIONYL BROMIDE AT 25°C

13. D. A. Long and R. T. Bailey, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 594.
14. E. W. Wartenberg and J. Goubeau, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1964, **329**, 269.
15. I. Lundqvist, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1958, **12**, 135.

Pyridine, α -picoline and quinoline are soluble in thionyl bromide. The plot of specific conductance against composition represented by molar ratio Base/SOBr₂ (Fig. 2) indicates the formation of 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 complexes in each case and in addition quinoline forms a 1 : 3 complex in solution. The conductance in each case decreases beyond 1 : 1 molar ratio because of the precipitation of solid adducts which on isolation have been found to have a general composition 2Base.SOBr₂. Isoquinoline, morpholine and benzylamine also provide white solids of general composition 2Base.SOBr₂. Like α -picoline, dimethylaniline forms a thick liquid adduct of a similar composition 2Base.SOBr₂. All these complexes are generally insoluble in common organic solvents but are slightly soluble in nitrobenzene. Their molar conductance in nitrobenzene is about 20 cm²ohm⁻¹mole⁻¹ which corresponds to their being uni-univalent electrolytes. Their ionic character is further supported by their high melting points and insolubility in non-polar solvents. Table I, records the molar, molal and specific conductance of these complexes along with other physical data. The relative strength of bases in thionyl bromide has been compared by calculating their molal conductance. These values are given in Table I and indicate the decreasing strengths of bases in thionyl bromide.

TABLE I

Nitrogen bases	Complex Base : SOBr ₂	m.p. °C	Molar con- ductance in nitrobenzene cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	Conc. in gram moles per 1000 g. of SOBr ₂	Sp. cond. in SOBr ₂ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Molal cond.
Dimethylaniline	2 : 1	—	20.0	0.01420	6.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.5 × 10 ⁻²
Pyridine	2 : 1	205—210	19.4	0.01053	4.04 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.8 × 10 ⁻²
α -Picoline	2 : 1	—	19.2	0.00151	1.85 × 10 ⁻³	3.0 × 10 ⁻²
Quinoline	2 : 1	120 - 125	18.6	0.02033	2.61 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.3 × 10 ⁻²
Isoquinoline	2 : 1	187	18.5	0.01550	1.82 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.2 × 10 ⁻²
Benzylamine	2 : 1	195	18.3	0.009187	1.92 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.1 × 10 ⁻³
Morpholine	2 : 1	190	18.0	0.01246	1.57 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.3 × 10 ⁻³

The nature of disolvates of pyridine, α -picoline and quinoline may be expressed as :

The monosolvates of pyridine, α -picoline and quinoline may ionise as :

The specific conductance of the trisolvate is more than that of the disolvate, which, in turn, is more than that of the monosolvate. In other cases as well the disolvates are more conducting than the monosolvates. The solvates 2-Base.SOBr₂ of pyridine, α -picoline, quinoline, isoquinoline, morpholine, benzylamine and dimethylaniline are all uni-univalent electrolytes and may, therefore, ionise as :

The infrared spectra of some of these solid adducts of thionyl bromide and of thionyl chloride with tertiary amines have been studied¹⁷. The results indicate that the nitrogen atom of the base molecule coordinates to the sulphur atom of the thionyl halide.

Acidic nature of thionyl bromide and the existence of the solvated bromide ion is elucidated by the isolation of complexes between quaternary ammonium bromides and thionyl bromide. Tetramethyl ammonium bromide and phenylbenzyl dimethyl ammonium bromide form (1 : 1) yellow solid complexes whereas tetraethyl ammonium bromide and phenylbenzyl diethyl ammonium bromide form (2 : 1) orange solid complexes with thionyl bromide. Their molar conductance in nitrobenzene indicates that the former complexes are uni-univalent whereas latter are uni-divalent in nature.

A study of the specific conductance of the solutions of tetramethyl and tetraethyl ammonium bromides in thionyl bromide is presented in Fig. 3. The quaternary ammonium bromides are expected to produce bromide ions in solution and thus act as an solvobases in

FIG 3—SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE OF TETRAMETHYL-AMMONIUM BROMIDE AND TETRAETHYLAMMONIUM BROMIDE IN THIONYL BROMIDE AT 25°C

thionyl bromide. Thionyl bromide ionises to give bromide ions, so it is expected to behave as a differentiating solvent for all substances which produce bromide ions. Hence, it may be possible to compare the strengths of the quaternary ammonium bromides in it. For this purpose, equivalent conductance (λ_e) of tetramethyl, tetraethyl, phenylbenzyl dimethyl and phenylbenzyl diethyl ammonium bromides has been plotted against the square root of the molar concentration (\sqrt{C}) in Fig. 4. The curves indicate that there does not seem to be much difference in their strengths. The values of equivalent conductance at infinite dilution (λ_0) cannot be so accurately extrapolated from these curves and for this

purpose λc is plotted against $1/\lambda c$ (Fig. 5). Straight lines on extrapolation, gives approximate values for $1/\lambda_0$, reciprocal of which gives λ_0 values.

λ_0 Values of quaternary ammonium bromides in $SOBr_2$

Compound	λ_0 values
$(CH_3)_4NBr$	31.2
$(C_2H_5)_4NBr$	25.0
$C_6H_5 \cdot C_6H_5CH_2 \cdot (CH_3)_2NBr$	28.6
$C_6H_5 \cdot C_6H_5CH_2 \cdot (C_2H_5)_2NBr$	22.2

The λ_0 values of these quaternary ammonium bromides in thionyl bromide are only moderately high. At concentrations higher than 0.40×10^{-2} gram equivalents per litre, the curves in Fig. 4 are almost straight lines and hence it may be assumed that the ionisation reactions are simple as :

Applying the law of mass action to the above equation (x), the dissociation constant K can be represented as :

$$K = \frac{\alpha C \cdot \alpha C}{(1-\alpha)C} = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{1-\alpha} \quad \dots (xi)$$

where α = degree of dissociation.

FIG 4. EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF QUATERNARY AMMONIUM BROMIDES IN THIONYL BROMIDE AT 25°C

According to Ostwalds' law of dilute solutions $\lambda c/\lambda_0$ can be used in place of α . The equation (xi), then takes the form :

$$K = \frac{\lambda^2 c \cdot C}{(\lambda_0 - \lambda c)\lambda_0} \quad \dots (xii)$$

From the equation, (xii), the approximate dissociation constants can be calculated directly by using known values of λc and λ_0 . Degree of dissociation (α) and the dissociation constant (K) of quaternary ammonium bromides at different concentrations are tabulated in Table II. The values indicate that the dissociation constant of phenylbenzyl-diethylammonium bromide is the highest.

The conductance of solutions of Lewis acids in thionyl bromide has been explained on the basis of the formation of $(SOBr)^+$ ion. This ion is the cation specific to the solvent

FIG.5— $c\lambda c$ VERSUS $1/\lambda c$ PLOTS OF QUATERNARY AMMONIUM BROMIDES IN THIONYL BROMIDE

TABLE II

α and K values of quaternary ammonium bromides in thionyl bromide

Quaternary ammonium bromide	Concentration $\times 10^2$ g.eq./litre (C)		α	K
$(CH_3)_4NBr$	0.4225	0.275	0.490	
	0.4900	0.275	0.510	
	0.6400	0.256	0.560	
	0.7225	0.246	0.578	
		Mean =	0.534	
$(C_2H_5)_4NBr$	0.4225	0.520	2.360	
	0.4900	0.490	2.307	
	0.6400	0.460	2.500	
	0.7225	0.440	2.470	
		Mean =	2.414	
$C_6H_5 \cdot C_6H_5CH_2(CH_3)_2NBr$	0.4225	0.314	0.604	
	0.4900	0.300	0.630	
	0.6400	0.280	0.679	
	0.7225	0.270	0.730	
		Mean =	0.666	
$C_6H_5 \cdot C_6H_5CH_2(C_2H_5)_2NBr$	0.4225	0.585	3.463	
	0.4900	0.550	3.293	
	0.6400	0.518	3.532	
	0.7225	0.495	3.580	
		Mean =	3.467	

thionyl bromide and therefore, the Lewis acids act as solvo acids in this medium. On the other hand quaternary ammonium bromides and tertiary nitrogen bases may act as ansolvo and solvo bases respectively. Based on these surmises, neutralisation reactions between solvo acids and ansolvo and solvo bases have been studied conductometrically. A change in the conductance of solutions of bases with the addition of acidic solutions has been studied and the relative conductance of a few representative systems has been plotted against concentration represented by molar ratio acid/base (Fig. 6). A summary of the conductometric titrations and the stoichiometric ratio of the reactants in the compound formed, is given in Table III.

TABLE III

Conductometric acid-base titrations in thionyl bromide

Titre	Titrant	Indicated stoichiometric ratios Titrant : Titre	
α -Picoline	SnBr ₄	1 : 2	1 : 1
Pyridine	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
Piperidine	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
Dimethylaniline	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
Quinoline	"	1 : 3	1 : 2
		1SnBr ₄ .1SOBr ₂ .1C ₉ H ₇ N (solid isolated)	
Tetramethylammonium bromide	"	1 : 2	
Tetraethylammonium bromide	"	1 : 2	
Pyridine	TiBr ₄	1 : 2	
α -Picoline	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
Quinoline	"	1 : 3,	1 : 2 and 1 : 1
Isoquinoline	"	1 : 3,	1 : 2 and 1 : 1 and
		1TiBr ₄ .1SOBr ₂ .1C ₉ H ₇ N (solid isolated)	
Tetramethylammonium bromide	"	1 : 2	
Tetraethylammonium bromide	"	1 : 2	
Tetramethylammonium bromide	AlBr ₃	1 : 3 and 1 : 1	
Pyridine	"	1 : 3	1 : 1
Dimethylaniline	"	1 : 3	1 : 1
α -Picoline	"	1 : 3	1 : 1
Quinoline	"	1 : 3	1 : 1
Quinoline	SbBr ₃	1 : 3	1 : 1
α -Picoline	"	—	1 : 1
Pyridine	"	—	1 : 1
Tetramethylammonium bromide	"	1 : 3	1 : 1
Tetraethylammonium bromide	"	1 : 3	1 : 1
Pyridine	SbBr ₃	1 : 2	1 : 1
α -Picoline	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
Quinoline	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
(CH ₃) ₄ NBr	"	1 : 2	1 : 1
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr	"	1 : 2	1 : 1

Acid-base titrations of pyridine, α -picoline, quinoline, piperidine, dimethylaniline, tetramethylammonium bromide and tetraethylammonium bromide against tin (IV) bromide have been carried out conductometrically but relative conductance of α -picoline system only has been plotted against molar ratio acid/base (Fig. 6). The formation of the normal salt at molar ratio of 0.5 may be explained as the result of the following reactions :

In case of quaternary ammonium bromides the neutralisation may be represented as :

The formation of acid salt at 1 : 1 molar ratio may be represented as follows :

The acid salt is more conducting than the normal salt because of the greater number of ionic species it produces in solution and the formation of the cation $(SOBr)^+$ which is specific to the solvent.

A light yellow solid complex $2 C_5H_5N \cdot SnBr_4$ separates out with pyridine. The formation of this complex is due to equilibrium (xiii). Its desolvation may be visualised as :

Desolvation does not change the coordination number of tin which remains six. The structure of the desolvated salt may be represented as :

In the titration of quinoline (Table III) as the molar ratio of 1 : 1 is approached, a pale yellow solid $(C_9H_7N \cdot SnBr_4 \cdot SOBr_2)$ separates out. The formation of the acid salt is represented by equilibrium (xv). Its desolvation may be represented as :

On the basis of penta coordination of tin, the complex may also be expected to have the following structure :

The conductometric titration curve of titanium (IV) bromide against pyridine in thionyl bromide (Fig. 6) shows a sharp decrease in conductance due to the separation of an insoluble complex. The increase beyond the molar ratio of 0.5 is due to the slow dissolution of this complex in excess of titanium (IV) bromide solution. The formation and desolvation of complexes of pyridine ($\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$), tetramethylammonium bromide [$\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$] and isoquinoline ($\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}.\text{SOBr}_2$) can be represented in a manner similar to that of tin (IV) bromide complexes.

In the conductometric titration of aluminium bromide solution against tetramethylammonium bromide (Fig. 6), the formation of complexes at acid/base molar ratios of 0.33 and 1 : 1, is indicated. The solid complex $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}.\text{AlBr}_3$ may be represented as :

The conductometric titration curve of antimony (III) bromide against quinoline (Fig. 6) is easily explained on the basis of hexa and tetra-coordination of antimony. The formation of 1 : 1 solid complexes with tetramethyl and tetraethylammonium bromides can be explained on the basis of tetra-coordination of antimony :

In the titration of antimony (V) bromide solution against pyridine (Fig. 6) and other bases (Table III), the formation of complexes at molar ratios 0.5 and 1 : 1 is indicated. The existence of complexes at a molar ratio of 0.5, though quite unusual are not unknown for

FIG 6—CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF LEWIS ACIDS AGAINST BASES IN THIONYL BROMIDE

antimony¹⁶. However, the existence of complex $(\text{B.SOBr})\text{SbBr}_6$ at a molar ratio of 1 : 1 and the formation of solid complexes with tetramethyl and tetraethyl ammonium bromides is explained on the basis of hexacoordination of antimony.

The polar nature of thionyl bromide and the possibility of release of bromide ions in solution which determines its usefulness as a brominating agent, is further confirmed by carrying out solvolytic reactions. Because of its instability above 80° all the reactions have been carried out below 70°.

Anhydrous arsenious oxide, bismuth oxide and ferric oxide combine with thionyl bromide at room temperature while zinc oxide, magnesium oxide, cadmium oxide and copper oxide react at higher temperatures (70°) giving rise to sulphur dioxide and the corresponding bromides. Aluminium oxide, chromium oxide, chromic anhydride, tin dioxide and selenium dioxide remain unaffected upto 70°. In analogy with phosphoryl bromide¹⁸ and acetyl halides^{19,20}, the reaction between an oxide and thionyl bromide may be represented as :

Bismuth, zinc and cadmium carbonate react vigorously at room temperature while calcium and barium carbonates react at 50–60° with the production of sulphur dioxide and carbon dioxide gases and corresponding metal bromides are left behind. Lithium, sodium, potassium and magnesium carbonates do not react upto 70°. The overall reaction may be represented as :

where M = divalent metal. The mechanism is similar for bismuth carbonate.

Tetramethylammonium iodide reacts at room temperature while potassium iodide and tetraethylammonium iodide do so at 50–60° producing free sulphur, iodine, sulphur dioxide gas and the corresponding bromide :

Thionyl iodide¹⁶ being unstable, decomposes as :

Sodium, potassium and ammonium formates react with thionyl bromide at 40–60° producing sulphur dioxide, hydrogen bromide and carbon monoxide gases and the corresponding bromides. Calcium formate does not react upto 70°.

18. S. K. Vasisht, Ph.D. thesis, Panjab University, Chandigarh, 1966.

19. R. C. Paul, D. Singh and S. S. Sandhu, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 319.

20. R. C. Paul, S. S. Sandhu and J. S. Bassi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 85.

Alkali metal (Li, Na and K) acetates react at room temperature, zinc and cadmium acetates do so at 40°, acetates of calcium, barium, strontium and magnesium react at 60° while acetates of manganese, cobalt, nickel and aluminium react at 70°. Sulphur dioxide escapes as a gas while acetyl bromide formed in each case distils over :

Di and trivalent metal acetates react in a similar fashion. The acetyl bromide formed, reacts with excess of metal acetate, if present, giving rise to acetic anhydride :

Organic fatty acids like acetic, propionic and butyric acids react with thionyl bromide at room temperature forming the corresponding acylbromides and hydrogen bromide and sulphur dioxide gases. The reaction with lower members is complete at room temperature while a little warming is needed with higher members :

Thionyl bromide reacts with liquid sulphur trioxide at room temperature forming sulphur dioxide gas and bromine :

Chlorosulphuric acid reacts with thionyl bromide at room temperature when the two are allowed to mix for sometime. Hydrogen bromide and sulphur dioxide gases are evolved while liquid bromine is left behind. Chlorosulphuric acid is already known to behave like an equimolar mixture of hydrogen chloride and sulphur trioxide²¹.

Taking into account the low specific conductance of thionyl bromide, its electrolysis was carried out after adding a base to it. Similar to the electrolysis of thionyl chloride,²² thionyl bromine gets electrolysed producing bromine at the anode where it remains in solution.

The primary product at the cathode, which is supposed to be (SOBr)⁺, further decomposes with the production of sulphur dioxide and bromine. The decomposition of (SOBr)⁺ may, therefore, be expected as :

Hence, the electrolysis supports the existence of the proposed ionic species in thionyl bromide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thionyl bromide was prepared by passing dry hydrogen bromide gas through thionyl chloride at 0° for about a week. The reddish liquid thus formed was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure and the fraction distilling at 55–57°/27 mm. was collected. The

21. R. C. Paul, S. K. Vasisht, K. C. Malhotra and S. S. Pahil, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 528.

22. H. Spandau, A. Beyer and F. Præugschat, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1960, **306**, 13.

orange liquid was twice fractionally distilled under reduced pressure and the middle fraction distilling at 55°/27 mm. was collected for use (Found Br 76.8%, required 76.88%). The specific conductance was found to be much below 1×10^{-7} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 20°.

Phenylbenzyl dimethyl ammonium bromide was prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of pure benzyl bromide and dimethylaniline. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hrs; the solid product was filtered, washed with benzene and ether and then subjected to vacuum. The white solid thus obtained was dissolved in acetone containing 10% by volume of methyl alcohol and the pure product was precipitated by addition of excess of ether. The solid was filtered, washed with ether, subjected to vacuum and then analysed.

Phenylbenzyl diethyl ammonium bromide was prepared by allowing an equimolar mixture of benzyl bromide and diethylaniline to stand for a week. The rest of procedure involving separation, purification, crystallisation, etc., is the same as described above.

Various solvents, Lewis acids, nitrogen bases, quaternary ammonium bromides and salts were purified by well known methods already in use.

Preparation of complexes

Complexes with Lewis acids : The complexes of aluminium bromide and chloride and boron (III) bromide with thionyl bromide (Table IV) have been prepared by adding the Lewis acids to ice-cold thionyl bromide.

TABLE IV

Complexes of Lewis acids with thionyl bromide

Lewis acid	Complex Acid:SOBr ₂	SOBr ₂ taken (g.)	Lewis acid added (g.)	Solvent used for washing	Br%		Al%		m.p. °C	Colour
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
AlBr ₃	1 : 1	5.0	6.0	CH ₂ Cl ₂	84.0	84.20	5.5	5.68	200(d)	Light yellow
AlCl ₃	1 : 1	8.0	5.0	CCl ₄	45.5	46.85	7.8	7.90	—	Light yellow
BBr ₃	1 : 1	4.4	6.0	—	87.0	87.20	—	—	95-100 (d)	Orange yellow

Complexes with nitrogen bases : Dilute solutions of the reactants in benzene were mixed after cooling them in an ice-bath. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with benzene and dried under vacuum. These complexes are generally insoluble in common organic solvents but are slightly soluble in nitrobenzene and thionyl bromide. These are given in Table V along with their analytical and physical data.

Complexes with quaternary ammonium bromides : Saturated solution of the quaternary ammonium bromide in thionyl bromide was treated with benzene or carbon tetrachloride, when two liquid layers were formed. The solvent layer was removed and the liquid was washed repeatedly to get a crystalline solid. All these complexes are soluble in nitrobenzene and thionyl bromide. Analytical data regarding these complexes are given in Table VI.

TABLE V

Complexes of thionyl bromide with nitrogen bases

Nitrogen base	Complex Base:SOBr ₂	SOBr ₂ taken (g.)	Base added (g.)	Br%		N %		m.p. °C	Colour
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
Pyridine	2 : 1	6.6	5.0	43.60	43.71	7.54	7.65	205	White
α-Picoline	2 : 1	5.6	5.0	40.49	40.61	6.98	7.10	—	Light yellow
Quinoline	2 : 1	4.0	5.0	34.46	34.34	5.88	6.01	120–25	White
Isoquinoline	2 : 1	4.0	5.0	34.45	34.34	5.92	6.01	187	Cream
Morpholine	2 : 1	6.0	5.0	41.00	41.88	7.00	7.14	190	White
Benzylamine	2 : 1	5.0	5.0	37.25	37.91	6.40	6.63	195	„
Dimethylaniline	2 : 1	4.0	5.0	35.35	35.50	6.20	6.22	—	Light yellow

TABLE VI

Quaternary ammonium bromide	Complex R ₄ NBr : SOBr ₂	Br%		N %		Colour
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
(CH ₃) ₄ NBr	1 : 1	66.2	66.30	3.8	3.87	Yellow
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr	2 : 1	50.8	50.95	4.4	4.46	Orange red
C ₆ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ .(CH ₃) ₂ NBr	1 : 1	47.8	48.00	2.6	2.80	Yellow
C ₆ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ .(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ NBr	2 : 1	37.4	37.70	3.2	3.30	Orange red

Acid-base neutralisation complexes in thionyl bromide : All the neutralisation complexes were prepared under similar conditions. A dilute solution of the base in thionyl bromide was treated with the solution of the Lewis acid in thionyl bromide. The mixing was done after cooling the reactants in an ice-bath. The solid complex was filtered, washed with dry benzene and then subjected to vacuum. The data regarding these complexes are tabulated in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Acid-base neutralisation complexes in thionyl bromide

Neutralisation complex	Metal %		Bromine %		Nitrogen %		m.p. °C	Colour
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
C ₂ H ₇ N.SnBr ₄ .SOBr ₂	15.20	15.30	61.70	61.88	1.75	1.80	207 dec.	Pale yellow
2C ₅ H ₅ N.SnBr ₄	19.80	19.90	53.50	53.63	4.58	4.69	> 300	„ Pale yellow
(iso)C ₆ H ₇ N.TiBr ₄ .SOBr ₂	6.75	6.81	67.54	67.10	1.90	1.98	> 260	Orange red
2C ₅ H ₅ N.TiBr ₄	8.95	9.12	60.67	60.84	2.58	2.66	> 260	Pale yellow
2(CH ₃) ₄ NBr.TiBr ₄	6.95	7.10	70.85	71.01	2.00	2.07	> 260	Red
(CH ₃) ₄ NBr.AlBr ₃	6.38	6.41	75.82	76.01	3.29	3.32	> 260	Yellow
(CH ₃) ₄ NBr.SbBr ₃	23.50	23.60	62.00	62.04	2.70	2.71	> 260	Orange red
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr.SbBr ₃	21.12	21.28	54.95	55.98	2.40	2.45	232	Orange red
(CH ₃) ₄ NBr.SbBr ₅	17.92	18.02	69.58	71.03	2.00	2.07	—	Brown
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr.SbBr ₅	16.60	16.64	65.00	65.60	1.90	1.91	—	Brown

Solvolytic reactions : The solute was added to a large excess of thionyl bromide at room temperature. The mixture was warmed in order to complete the reaction but the temperature was never allowed to go beyond 70°. The gaseous product was tested and any liquid formed was distilled over while the solid left behind was analysed.

Conductance measurements : The resistance of the solution was measured as already described by Paul *et al.*²³.

Electrolysis : It was carried out in a cell, having platinum electrodes at the bottom of the two limbs connected near the bottom by another small tube. A solution of known concentration was added into the limbs to cover the electrodes. A source of direct current or a set of dry batteries was connected with the cell in series and the reactions taking place near the electrodes were studied.

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